

Synthesis, structural elucidation, microbial and antioxidant activities of mixed ligand Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes

S. Salon Mary^a, J. Dharmaraja^b, J. Balamurugan^c, P. Subbaraj^d and S. Shobana^{*e}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Gulf Model School, Al Muhaisnah, Qusais-13683, Dubai, UAE

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Sree Sowdambika College of Engineering, Chettikurichi, Aruppukottai-626 134, Virudhunagar District, Tamilnadu, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Sri Vidya College of Engineering College and Technology, P. Kumarlingapuram, Virudhunagar-626 005, Tamilnadu, India

^dDepartment of Chemistry, Devanga Arts College (Autonomous), Aruppukottai-626 101, Virudhunagar District, Tamilnadu, India

^eDepartment of Chemistry, Rajas Institute of Technology for Women, Ozhuginasery, Nagercoil-629 001, Kanyakumari District, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : prakash24176@gmail.com

Abstract : A series of novel bioactive mononuclear N₃O type mixed ligand MAB complexes (1-4) [M^{II} = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}; A = 5-fluorouracil (5-FU); B = L-histamine (hist)] were synthesized and structurally characterized by various physico-chemical, spectral, thermal and morphological studies. From the analytical and spectral studies, both the ligands act as bidentate and binds with the M^{II} ions to form a stable octahedral geometry. Thermal (TGA/DTA) studies show loss of coordinated water and acetate molecules in the initial stage. Micro-crystalline nature with homogeneous morphology of the complexes is confirmed from Powder XRD and SEM analysis. Moreover, Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes show more potent microbial and antioxidant activities.

Keywords : 5-Fluorouracil, mixed ligand complexes, spectral, pharmacological study.

Introduction

Recently, an extensive work has been carried out in biological, industrial, medicinal and clinical studies of the mixed ligand complexes contain bioactive hard and soft donor hetero N, S and/O atoms^{1,2}. Halogen substituted pyrimidine (5-fluorouracil) derivatives have been employed in clinical, medical and chemotherapeutic fields for curing various tumor cells in our human body^{3,4} and more effective in the treatment of Bowen's disease (BD) in skin. Heterocyclic imidazole ring moiety containing organic L-histamine ligand shows potent catalytic activities of the numerous enzymes⁵ and widely used in fungal, clinical, analytical, antiprotozoal and antihypertensive fields. In continuation of our recent reports⁶⁻⁹, the major goal of the present work is to synthesize and structurally characterize the novel N₃O type mixed ligand Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes from 5-fluorouracil (5-FU:A)

and L-histamine (hist:B). Moreover, both *in vitro* microbial and antioxidant activities of free 5-FU and their complexes have also been studied.

Experimental

Procedure and physical measurements :

All the chemicals and solvents were extra pure AnalaR grade (Sigma-Aldrich and Fluka) and used without further purification. 5-Fluorouracil (10 mmol) was completely dissolved in aqueous solution (10 ml) containing minimum amount of concentrated ammonia and added dropwise to an aqueous solution of metal acetate (10 mmol/10 ml) and stirred. To this solution, add aqueous solution of L-histamine (10 mmol/10 ml) and refluxed for 5-6 h. The resulting solution was reduced to 1/3 in a water bath. The solid complex precipitate was collected by vacuum filtration and dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous CaCl₂ (Yield :

45–65%). The synthesised mixed ligand complexes were structurally characterized by various physico-chemical and spectral techniques which were carried out as described earlier^{6–9}. *In vitro* microbial and antioxidant activities of free 5-FU and their complexes were made in three replicate for each and the detailed procedures were described earlier^{6–9}.

Results and discussion

All the mixed ligand MAB complexes have been found to be colored, air stable and non-hygroscopic in nature. The analytical data together with some physico-chemical properties of the complexes are summarized in Table 1. The observed analytical and spectral values suggest that the complexes have 1 : 1 : 1 (metal : 5-FU : L-hist) stoichiometry with non-electrolytic nature. From vibrational spectral data (KBr pellet, cm^{-1}) of free 5-FU(A) ligand shows some typical peaks at 1704 and 1685, 1513 and 1430 and 1470 cm^{-1} due to vibrations of carbonyl oxygen at $\nu(\text{C}_2=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}_4=\text{O})$, amine and amide nitrogen at $\delta(\text{N-H})$ of N_1 and N_3 and fluorine of $\nu(\text{C}_5-\text{F})$ groups in pyrimidine ring respectively. On complexation, the peaks at 1685 and 1430 cm^{-1} were shifted towards lower frequency (1654–1685 and 1402–1415 cm^{-1}) regions and the remaining peaks were unaffected which proves that their non-involvement in coordination¹⁰. Similarly, L-histamine(B) ligand binds the M^{II} ions in bidentate manner¹⁰ via imidazole ring-N and side chain amino-N of $\nu(\text{NH}_2)$ groups respectively. From this study, both 5-FU(A) and hist(B) ligands act as bidentate to form a stable

chelate through deprotonated- N_3 and $\text{C}_4=\text{O}$ of carbonyl oxygen and imidazole ring-N and side chain amino-N atoms respectively. This is further confirmed from the appearance of some new peaks in low frequency regions at 434–470 cm^{-1} and 523–551 cm^{-1} for $\nu(\text{M-O})$ and $\nu(\text{M-N})$ stretching respectively¹⁰. Furthermore, in all the complexes, the band in the region 1572–1621 and 1358–1399 cm^{-1} and 3300–3450 cm^{-1} , 817–845 cm^{-1} and 716–734 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to vibration of the coordinated acetate and water molecules respectively¹⁰.

The electronic environment of the mixed ligand complexes (1–4) were recorded in DMSO medium in the range of 200–1100 nm and this complexes show low molar absorptivity. The absorption region, spectral band assignment and proposed geometry of the complexes are given in Table 1. The obtained spectral data coupled with magnetic moment values suggest that distorted octahedral geometry around the central M^{II} ions¹¹. The proton NMR spectrum of mixed ligand Zn^{II} complex was recorded in d_6 -dimethylsulfoxide solution using TMS as internal standard. The entire protons present in the Zn^{II} complex are well established in their expected regions¹². From ^1H NMR spectra, both 5-FU(A) and L-hist(B) ligands bind the Zn^{II} ion via, deprotonated- N_3 and carbonyl oxygen ($\text{C}_4=\text{O}$) and imidazole ring-N and side chain amino-N groups respectively which reinforces the conclusions drawn from the IR spectra. Furthermore, the spectrum shows a peak centered at 4.75 ppm due to the presence of coordinated water molecules¹² and there is no significant variation in all other signals. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA/DTA) for the synthesised MAB complexes in the range

Table 1. Various physico-chemical and electronic spectral data of MAB complexes

Complex	Empirical formula ^a	Mol. weight	Λ_m ($\text{S cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	M.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Colour	λ_{max} (cm^{-1})	Band assignments	Geometry	μ_{eff}
CoAB	$\text{CoC}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_5\text{O}_5\text{F}$	376.3	15.22	240	Purple	9750 13300 19630	$^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}(F)$ $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4A_{2g}(F)$ $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P)$	Octahedral	4.84
NiAB	$\text{NiC}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_5\text{O}_5\text{F}$	376.2	17.40	252	Green	10150 15890 25680	$^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^3T_{2g}(F)$ $^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(F)$ $^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(P)$	Octahedral	3.01
CuAB	$\text{CuC}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_5\text{O}_5\text{F}$	380.9	22.50	> 270	Brown	14690 29235	$^2E_g \rightarrow ^2T_{2g}$ LMCT ($n \rightarrow \pi^*$)	Distorted octahedral	1.84
ZnAB	$\text{ZnC}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_5\text{O}_5\text{F}$	382.8	20.25	> 270	White	26576	LMCT ($\text{M} \leftarrow \text{N}$)	Distorted octahedral	Dia.

^aC, H and N analysis are within the limit of ± 0.3 – 0.4% ; A = 5-Fluorouracil (5-FU) and B = L-histamine (hist).

of ambient to 900 °C. The decomposition of Zn^{II} complex follows in three steps, the first and second steps correspond to the removal of coordinated water and acetate molecules. The organic ligand moieties are eliminated in the third step and finally it leaves air stable metal oxide as residue. The obtained results are well agreed with the composition of metal chelates. Kinetic order of the decomposition was also calculated by the modified Horowitz and Metzger equation and observed C_s (0.53) value indicates that the decomposition follows first order kinetics.

Powder X-ray diffraction and SEM studies are useful to determine the purity, phase identification, structure, particle size and morphology of the complexes. The Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes (1-3) were recorded in the range of 0–70° and the crystallite size was estimated from the main XRD peak by using the Scherrer's equation ($D = 0.9\lambda/\beta \cos \theta$). From the diffractogram (Fig. 1a), a large number of weak peaks was observed which indicate that uniform phase with no impurity and the average grain size value for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes (1-3) are 22,

18 and 28 μm respectively. Also, this XRD pattern shows microcrystalline nature of the complexes and this behaviour is due to the incorporation of water and acetate molecules into the coordination sphere. However, we are ineffective to grow a single crystal of these complexes. Morphology and particle size of Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}-5-FU(A)-hist(B) complexes (2 and 4) were investigated from SEM studies. From SEM pictograph, the mixed ligand complexes have uniform matrix with smooth interface having perfect regular shape of homogeneous phase material. A small rocky layer by layer like morphology for the Ni^{II} complex with the particle size 12 μm and an irregularly broken brick like morphological appearance (Fig. 1b) with the particle size of 22 μm were found for Zn^{II} complex. Based on the analytical and spectral studies indicate that all the complexes have octahedral geometry. *In vitro* microbial activities of 5-fluorouracil and their complexes (1-4) were tested against five pathogenic bacterial and three fungal species by well diffusion method using agar as nutrient and their representative graph is shown in Fig. 2(a). The measured zone of inhibition (in mm) against

Fig. 1. (a) XRD pattern of complexes (1-3) and (b) SEM image of complex (4).

Fig. 2. *In vitro* (a) microbial and (b) antioxidant activities of 5-FU and its complexes.

the growth of the species was compared with commercially available tetracycline (antibacterial control) and amphotericin (antifungal control) drugs. All the complexes show remarkable microbial activities as compared to 5-FU ligand and these increased activities can be explained on the basis of Overtone's concept and Tweedy's chelation hypothesis¹³. Antioxidant activities were investigated *in vitro* by DPPH free radical scavenging methods and their representative graph is shown in Fig. 2(b). Ascorbic acid was used as control and all the analysis were done in three replicates. Decreasing the ability of DPPH radical is determined by the decrease in its absorbance at 517 nm (blank) which can be induced by the antioxidant. From the results, it is seen that Cu^{II} complex has higher activities than free ligand and also 5-fluorouracil alone shows some sensible activity.

Conclusion

In the present study, mixed ligand complexes containing M^{II} ions with 5-fluorouracil (5-FU:A) and L-histamine (hist:B) were synthesised and characterized by various spectral and analytical techniques. From the spectral studies demonstrate that all the complexes have distorted octahedral geometry. The powder XRD and SEM analysis show that all the complexes display sharp crystalline peaks with well-defined microcrystalline nature with uniform surface morphology. Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes show remarkable microbial and antioxidant activities than free ligand.

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